

Rac-4f

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-167-RAC-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	63	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 167 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/27/2021 5:20:17 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/28/2021 10:20:05 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.522	1347702	49.76	92783
2	12.912	1360972	50.24	

Asy-4f

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-168-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	78	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 168
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/27/2021 9:36:47 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/28/2021 10:22:01 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.488	168525	2.13	12131
2	12.830	7742442	97.87	401480